

Determining stellar properties of massive stars in NGC 346 in the SMC with a Bayesian statistic technique

Additional Information

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1 Introduction

Additional information in support of the Astronomy & Astrophysics article of the same name.
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Table 1: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 18.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s ⁻¹
57611.32930492	164.5 ± 1.3
57613.24629853	167.5 ± 2.0
57617.23462962	164.7 ± 1.4
57618.10327055	165.0 ± 1.6
57620.14865186	166.9 ± 1.0
57620.19041780	166.3 ± 1.2
57621.20640006	165.5 ± 1.5
57621.24834448	165.7 ± 1.3

2 Individual star discussions

SSN 18

Figure 1: SSN 18 Bayesian fit results. *Top left*: Stellar parameters Probability Distribution, presented as a corner plot. *Top right*: RV probability distribution, present as a violin plot per observation. *Bottom*: Median sample results used to generate a synthetic spectrum (Red) for the employed diagnostic lines, compared to the MUSE observations (Blue), each shifted by median RV. Shaded red represents regions masked from the fitting process, either because the line is not used but still shown here, or because of nebular contamination to the observed line.

SSN 18 has previously been classified with the spectral type of O6.5V (Massey et al. 1989). The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 1. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 18 (*Blue*) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Figure 3: SSN 22 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 22 presented in Fig. 3. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 2. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 22 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 2: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 22.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s^{-1}
57611.32930492	166.8 ± 3.1
57613.24629853	173.4 ± 2.2
57613.28828952	170.0 ± 2.3
57617.23462962	173.3 ± 3.2
57620.14865186	177.2 ± 7.9
57620.19041780	173.6 ± 4.9
57620.23261681	168.9 ± 4.7
57621.20640006	167.7 ± 3.5
57621.24834448	169.7 ± 5.1
57622.14718256	169.4 ± 2.6

Figure 5: SSN 31 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 31 presented in Fig. 5. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 3. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 31 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 3: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 31.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s ⁻¹
57611.32930492	164.7 ± 1.4
57613.24629853	162.4 ± 1.9
57613.28828952	167.7 ± 1.4
57617.23462962	163.3 ± 1.2
57618.10327055	166.7 ± 1.3
57620.14865186	161.9 ± 1.1
57620.19041780	163.7 ± 1.3
57620.23261681	162.5 ± 1.3
57621.20640006	162.4 ± 1.2
57621.24834448	161.9 ± 1.2
57622.14718256	163.4 ± 1.5

Figure 7: SSN 32 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 32 presented in Fig. 7. The RV violin plot show large variations and these meet the criteria for SB1 classification. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 4. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 8

Figure 8: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 32 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 4: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 32.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s ⁻¹
57611.32930492	159.9 ± 1.7
57613.24629853	158.5 ± 2.8
57613.28828952	158.4 ± 2.2
57617.23462962	151.7 ± 0.7
57618.10327055	151.3 ± 0.3
57620.14865186	159.2 ± 1.9
57620.19041780	157.1 ± 1.9
57620.23261681	159.1 ± 3.7
57621.20640006	186.6 ± 11.2
57621.24834448	163.2 ± 3.1
57622.14718256	165.9 ± 1.9

Figure 9: SSN 33 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

SSN 33 had a spectral type of O8V (Massey et al. 1989). Result presented in Fig. 9. Dufton et al. (2019) categorise this object as an SB1 but the RV results in this work do not meet the threshold for SB1 adopted in this work. Despite this, SSN 33 has previously classified as an SB1 candidate by Dufton et al. (2019). A visual inspection of the RV distribution does appear to show a trend of changing RVs as the observations proceed over 11 days. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 5. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 10

Figure 10: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 33 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 5: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 33.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s ⁻¹
57611.32930492	169.7 ± 1.1
57613.24629853	170.5 ± 1.8
57613.28828952	169.8 ± 1.5
57617.23462962	168.9 ± 1.2
57618.10327055	164.3 ± 1.5
57620.14865186	165.9 ± 1.5
57620.19041780	167.0 ± 1.1
57620.23261681	166.0 ± 1.3
57621.20640006	167.1 ± 1.2
57621.24834448	166.5 ± 1.4
57622.14718256	164.6 ± 1.3

Figure 11: SSN 34 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

SSN 34 has previously been given the spectral type O9.5V (Massey et al. 1989). Results are presented in Fig. 11. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 6. SSN 34 has previously been classified as an SB1 candidate by Dufton et al. (2019). The RVs shown in the violin plot do indicate a changing trend of changing RV which strongly agrees with this classification but the results do not meet the 4σ significance criteria adopted (Sana et al. 2013). The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 12

Figure 12: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 34 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 6: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 34.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s^{-1}
57611.32930492	150.0 ± 5.1
57613.24629853	155.1 ± 1.9
57613.28828952	154.5 ± 1.8
57618.10327055	158.6 ± 2.2
57620.14865186	158.2 ± 1.3
57620.19041780	157.3 ± 1.1
57620.23261681	158.2 ± 1.4
57621.20640006	161.0 ± 1.4
57621.24834448	161.6 ± 1.6
57622.14718256	162.1 ± 1.7

Figure 13: SSN 36 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

SSN 36 has a spectral type from [Massey et al. \(1989\)](#) of O8V. Full result presented in Fig. 13. This object meets the criteria adopted to be considered an SB1 candidate. It has previously been classified as an SB1 ([Dufton et al. 2019](#)). The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 7. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 14

Figure 14: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 36 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 7: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 36.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s ⁻¹
57611.32930492	196.4 ± 1.0
57613.24629853	171.2 ± 3.6
57613.28828952	172.4 ± 4.1
57617.23462962	155.1 ± 1.5
57618.10327055	155.4 ± 1.6
57620.14865186	157.2 ± 1.1
57620.19041780	159.8 ± 1.3
57620.23261681	159.9 ± 1.8
57621.20640006	164.1 ± 2.2
57621.24834448	166.0 ± 1.1
57622.14718256	164.8 ± 2.0

Figure 15: SSN 40 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 40 are presented in Fig. 15. Massey et al. (1989) previous classified this object as a B0V. While the trend shown in the changing median RVs fulfils the minimum difference criteria of $> 10 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ to be considered an SB1 candidate, the adopted 4σ significance criteria is not met. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 8. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 16

Figure 16: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 40 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of Luminosity fitting.

Table 8: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 40.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s^{-1}
57611.32930492	159.5 ± 1.9
57613.24629853	155.0 ± 2.1
57613.28828952	154.3 ± 2.1
57617.23462962	160.1 ± 3.3
57618.10327055	156.5 ± 1.7
57620.14865186	161.3 ± 4.4
57620.19041780	158.7 ± 2.4
57621.20640006	156.2 ± 1.8
57621.24834448	167.1 ± 12.3
57622.14718256	169.5 ± 4.2

Table 9: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 41.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s ⁻¹
57611.32930492	169.1 ± 1.1
57613.24629853	168.8 ± 2.8
57613.28828952	168.1 ± 1.7
57617.23462962	162.3 ± 1.9
57618.10327055	168.6 ± 1.4
57620.14865186	157.4 ± 1.5
57620.19041780	158.1 ± 1.2
57620.23261681	157.0 ± 1.1
57621.20640006	159.7 ± 1.7
57621.24834448	163.2 ± 1.6
57622.14718256	166.9 ± 1.7

SSN 41

Figure 17: SSN 41 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 41 presented in Fig. 17. This object has a previous spectral type of O7.5V (Massey et al. 1989). This object meets the criteria adopted to be considered an SB1 candidate. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 9. No HST observations are available from Rickard et al. (2022) to measure the luminosity of SSN 41 using the selected method.

Figure 18: SSN 43 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 43 presented in Fig. 18. The median RV differences between epochs are sufficient and significant enough to classify this object as an SB1. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 10. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 19.

Figure 19: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 43 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 10: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 43.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s^{-1}
57613.28828952	169.6 ± 3.2
57617.23462962	153.0 ± 1.4
57620.14865186	163.6 ± 2.6
57620.19041780	157.3 ± 1.9
57620.23261681	156.5 ± 2.6
57621.20640006	167.4 ± 2.2
57621.24834448	165.3 ± 2.6
57622.14718256	151.1 ± 1.5

Table 11: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 44.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s ⁻¹
57611.32930492	159.8 ± 5.6
57613.28828952	159.4 ± 6.3
57618.10327055	166.8 ± 1.8
57620.14865186	170.1 ± 1.2
57620.19041780	168.2 ± 1.2
57620.23261681	163.8 ± 2.5
57622.14718256	157.6 ± 3.6

SSN 44

Figure 20: SSN 44 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Massey et al. (1989) have previously assigned SSN 44 the spectral type of O8V. Result for SSN 44 presented in Fig. 20. The RV differences between epochs are not significant enough to classify this object as an SB1. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 11. No HST observations are available from Rickard et al. (2022) to measure the luminosity of SSN 44.

Figure 21: SSN 46 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

The variability in the RV results from the sampler are significant based on the adopted criteria, leading to the classification of SSN 46 as an SB1 candidate. However the He lines hint at multiple features and further observations may change this classification from SB1 to SB2. SB2 classification is also supported by the unusual slope of the HST SED, possibly showing two peaks (Fig. 22). However the result returned by the sampler is well converged and suggests a plausible single star fit, so for the sake of this work this star is considered an SB1, with this important note that further investigations are warranted.

Massey et al. (1989) give this object the spectral type of O6V:. Result for SSN 46 presented in Fig. 21. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 12.

Table 12: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 46.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s^{-1}
57611.32930492	140.6 ± 0.7
57613.24629853	198.0 ± 2.5
57613.28828952	189.2 ± 3.6
57617.23462962	151.4 ± 0.9
57618.10327055	199.2 ± 3.9
57620.14865186	175.6 ± 7.8
57620.19041780	167.6 ± 1.5
57620.23261681	165.7 ± 1.9
57621.20640006	139.3 ± 3.7
57621.24834448	150.8 ± 3.4
57622.14718256	153.8 ± 1.8

Figure 22: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 46 (*Blue*) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 13: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 50.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s^{-1}
57611.32930492	173.5 ± 0.9
57613.24629853	170.7 ± 1.1
57613.28828952	172.8 ± 4.1
57617.23462962	175.4 ± 6.0
57620.14865186	172.6 ± 1.0
57620.19041780	172.2 ± 1.2
57621.20640006	172.6 ± 1.6
57621.24834448	171.8 ± 1.5
57622.14718256	174.7 ± 1.0

SSN 50

Figure 23: SSN 50 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Both the previous spectral type of O7V (Massey et al. 1989) There is very little variation in the sampler RV results. Full sampler result presented in Fig. 23. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 13. No HST observations from Rickard et al. (2022) are available for SSN 50 to measure the luminosity.

Figure 24: SSN 55 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

SSN 55 has very minimal variation in RV results between epoch. Result are presented in Fig. 24. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 14. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 25.

Figure 25: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 55 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 14: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 55.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s ⁻¹
57611.32930492	156.6 ± 2.1
57613.24629853	156.3 ± 2.6
57613.28828952	161.1 ± 2.7
57617.23462962	157.9 ± 2.6
57618.10327055	155.3 ± 2.1
57620.14865186	163.4 ± 2.4
57620.19041780	156.3 ± 2.3
57620.23261681	157.0 ± 2.7
57621.24834448	161.1 ± 2.3
57622.14718256	157.7 ± 2.2

Table 15: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 56.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s ⁻¹
57611.32930492	158.2 ± 1.6
57613.24629853	163.1 ± 2.5
57613.28828952	157.5 ± 1.6
57617.23462962	156.2 ± 1.9
57618.10327055	156.6 ± 1.8
57620.14865186	160.3 ± 2.1
57620.19041780	159.0 ± 1.7
57620.23261681	160.0 ± 1.7
57621.24834448	160.5 ± 1.9
57622.14718256	157.8 ± 2.1

SSN 56

Figure 26: SSN 56 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 56 show minimal change in RV between different epochs. Full results are presented in Fig. 26. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 15. No HST observations for SSN 56 are available to measure the luminosity from Rickard et al. (2022).

Figure 27: SSN 57 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 57 presented in Fig. 27. While an inspection of the results for the RV parameters shown in the violin plot may suggest binarity, the adopted 4σ significance criteria is not met. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 16. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 28.

Figure 28: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 57 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 16: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 57.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s^{-1}
57611.32930492	167.2 ± 1.7
57613.28828952	164.0 ± 2.4
57618.10327055	158.2 ± 6.5
57620.14865186	166.5 ± 2.5
57620.19041780	168.1 ± 1.8
57620.23261681	162.8 ± 4.8
57621.24834448	187.2 ± 7.4
57622.14718256	185.5 ± 9.4

Figure 29: SSN 59 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 59 presented in Fig. 29.

the SB1 criteria adopted from Sana et al. (2013) are satisfied, this entirely due to the one outlier RV result (MJD 57611). This preliminary classification is ignored and instead SSN 59 is reported as a single star. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 17. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 30.

Figure 30: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 59 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 17: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 59.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s^{-1}
57613.24629853	159.7 ± 3.3
57613.28828952	156.5 ± 3.9
57620.14865186	155.3 ± 2.1
57620.19041780	157.4 ± 1.7
57620.23261681	153.0 ± 5.3
57621.20640006	162.9 ± 13.8
57621.24834448	154.1 ± 8.8
57622.14718256	160.1 ± 3.2

Figure 31: SSN 62 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Massey et al. (1989) give SSN 62 a spectral type of O9V. Result for SSN 62 presented in Fig. 31. The RV shifts are significant and qualify SSN 62 as an SB1. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 18. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 32.

Figure 32: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 62 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 18: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 62.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s^{-1}
57613.24629853	186.5 ± 13.0
57613.28828952	171.1 ± 5.1
57617.23462962	156.5 ± 4.0
57620.19041780	159.5 ± 2.6
57620.23261681	153.1 ± 7.1
57621.20640006	189.3 ± 3.5
57621.24834448	193.2 ± 5.0
57622.14718256	203.3 ± 6.0

Figure 33: SSN 77 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 77 presented in Fig. 33. The RV violin plot shows the sampler result for RV and shows that one observation would qualify this target as an SB1 candidate. However, as the remaining median RVs are all grouped around $RV \sim 152 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ this one median RV is treated as erroneous and so SSN 77 is not considered an SB1 candidate based on these MUSE observations. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 19. No HST observations for SSN 77 are available to measure the luminosity from Rickard et al. (2022).

Table 19: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 77.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s $^{-1}$
57611.32930492	152.2 ± 5.8
57613.24629853	152.5 ± 1.3
57613.28828952	152.2 ± 0.7
57617.23462962	195.5 ± 3.0
57618.10327055	157.3 ± 4.9
57620.14865186	151.5 ± 0.9
57620.19041780	152.2 ± 1.3
57621.24834448	151.8 ± 1.4
57622.14718256	150.8 ± 0.5

Figure 34: SSN 83 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 83 presented in Fig. 34. The median RV differences between epochs are sufficient and significant enough to classify this object as an SB1. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 20. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 35.

Figure 35: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 83 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 20: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 83.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s ⁻¹
57611.32930492	189.5 ± 3.3
57611.32930492	189.5 ± 3.4
57613.24629853	171.0 ± 5.2
57613.28828952	187.1 ± 5.8
57617.23462962	169.5 ± 2.3
57618.10327055	167.4 ± 4.0
57620.14865186	167.5 ± 1.8
57620.19041780	171.5 ± 6.7
57620.23261681	168.6 ± 3.6
57621.20640006	169.5 ± 2.6
57621.24834448	176.1 ± 5.7

Figure 36: SSN 84 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 84 presented in Fig. 36. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 21. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 37.

Figure 37: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 84 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 21: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 84.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s^{-1}
57611.32930492	158.9 ± 9.0
57613.24629853	160.2 ± 3.1
57613.28828952	160.6 ± 4.2
57617.23462962	153.7 ± 4.1
57618.10327055	139.2 ± 12.4
57620.19041780	139.1 ± 8.5
57621.24834448	145.0 ± 7.5

Figure 38: SSN 88 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result presented in Fig. 38. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 22. No HST observations for SSN 88 are available to measure the luminosity from Rickard et al. (2022).

Table 22: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 88.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s^{-1}
57611.32930492	158.9 ± 1.1
57613.24629853	168.6 ± 2.7
57613.28828952	162.9 ± 2.4
57617.23462962	165.9 ± 1.8
57618.10327055	165.6 ± 2.4
57620.14865186	164.4 ± 2.8
57620.19041780	164.0 ± 2.0
57620.23261681	162.2 ± 2.6
57621.20640006	165.8 ± 1.9
57621.24834448	165.4 ± 2.2
57622.14718256	160.4 ± 2.0

Figure 39: SSN 100 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 100 presented in Fig. 39. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 23. No HST observations for SSN 100 are available to measure the luminosity from Rickard et al. (2022).

Table 23: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 100.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s^{-1}
57620.14865186	153.7 ± 3.1
57620.19041780	153.1 ± 4.2
57620.23261681	155.4 ± 2.6
57621.20640006	153.5 ± 12.8
57622.14718256	152.8 ± 12.6

Figure 40: SSN 102 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 102 presented in Fig. 40. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 24. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 41.

Figure 41: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 102 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 24: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 102.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s ⁻¹
57611.32930492	179.1 ± 3.6
57613.28828952	168.4 ± 2.5
57617.23462962	171.4 ± 5.5
57618.10327055	187.3 ± 4.7
57620.14865186	168.0 ± 1.8
57620.19041780	169.7 ± 2.5
57620.23261681	171.6 ± 8.2
57621.20640006	168.0 ± 2.6
57621.24834448	171.1 ± 10.2
57622.14718256	168.2 ± 1.8

Figure 42: SSN 105 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 105 presented in Fig. 42. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 25. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 43.

Figure 43: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 105 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 25: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 105.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s ⁻¹
57611.32930492	165.9 ± 4.9
57613.24629853	164.9 ± 2.6
57617.23462962	162.0 ± 3.7
57618.10327055	164.0 ± 4.1
57620.14865186	161.2 ± 3.1
57621.20640006	156.5 ± 1.5
57621.24834448	157.1 ± 2.7
57622.14718256	161.8 ± 2.7

Figure 44: SSN 109 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 109 presented in Fig. 44. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 26. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 45.

Figure 45: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 109 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 26: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 109.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s^{-1}
57611.32930492	157.1 ± 9.6
57613.24629853	157.2 ± 9.3
57617.23462962	155.0 ± 2.3
57620.14865186	155.7 ± 4.6
57620.19041780	153.6 ± 2.1
57621.24834448	152.5 ± 2.0
57622.14718256	153.1 ± 2.3

Figure 46: SSN 110 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 110 presented in Fig. 46. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 27. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 47.

Figure 47: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 110 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 27: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 110.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s ⁻¹
57611.32930492	159.7 ± 3.5
57613.28828952	166.7 ± 4.0
57617.23462962	161.0 ± 1.8
57618.10327055	156.0 ± 2.0
57620.14865186	157.9 ± 12.3
57620.19041780	185.9 ± 9.8
57621.20640006	165.6 ± 6.7
57621.24834448	167.9 ± 3.5
57622.14718256	168.7 ± 5.9

Figure 48: SSN 122 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 122 presented in Fig. 48. The median RV differences between epochs are sufficient and significant enough to classify this object as an SB1. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 28. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 49.

Figure 49: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 122 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 28: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 122.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s^{-1}
57613.24629853	155.7 ± 3.8
57617.23462962	188.4 ± 4.4
57622.14718256	192.5 ± 5.8

Figure 50: SSN 142 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 142 presented in Fig. 50. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 29. No HST observations for SSN 142 are available to measure the luminosity from Rickard et al. (2022).

Table 29: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 142.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s^{-1}
57617.23462962	161.3 ± 3.1
57621.24834448	160.3 ± 2.2

Figure 51: SSN 171 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 171 presented in Fig. 51. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 30. No HST observations for SSN 171 are available to measure the luminosity from Rickard et al. (2022).

Table 30: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 171.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s^{-1}
57611.32930492	156.3 ± 2.4
57613.24629853	153.6 ± 2.0
57613.28828952	156.0 ± 2.6
57617.23462962	158.0 ± 2.1
57618.10327055	161.0 ± 4.1
57620.14865186	156.7 ± 1.7
57620.19041780	161.6 ± 1.1
57620.23261681	157.6 ± 3.3
57621.20640006	153.4 ± 2.3
57621.24834448	157.2 ± 2.7
57622.14718256	156.4 ± 2.7

Figure 52: SSN 177 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 177 presented in Fig. 52. The median RV differences between epochs are sufficient and significant enough to classify this object as an SB1. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 31. No HST observations for SSN 177 are available to measure the luminosity from Rickard et al. (2022).

Table 31: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 177.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s^{-1}
57611.32930492	197.5 ± 13.2
57613.24629853	197.4 ± 3.9
57613.28828952	158.2 ± 2.1
57620.14865186	168.6 ± 6.8
57620.19041780	167.6 ± 4.4
57622.14718256	167.3 ± 3.0

Figure 53: SSN 188 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 188 presented in Fig. 53. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 32. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 54.

Figure 54: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 188 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 32: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 188.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s ⁻¹
57611.32930492	156.4 ± 2.6
57613.24629853	156.1 ± 2.4
57613.28828952	156.6 ± 2.3
57617.23462962	162.5 ± 3.8
57620.19041780	154.8 ± 2.1
57620.23261681	158.0 ± 4.5
57621.20640006	155.7 ± 2.0
57621.24834448	155.5 ± 2.2
57622.14718256	156.0 ± 2.0

Figure 55: SSN 193 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 193 presented in Fig. 55. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 33. The luminosity fitting is shown in Fig. 56.

Figure 56: Observed UV spectrum and HST photometry of SSN 193 (Blue) fit to PoWR synthetic SED taken from the nearest SMC grid model, for the purpose of luminosity fitting.

Table 33: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 193.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s ⁻¹
57611.32930492	167.6 ± 2.2
57613.24629853	165.9 ± 3.6
57617.23462962	163.7 ± 5.4
57620.14865186	161.5 ± 2.5
57620.19041780	160.9 ± 3.6
57620.23261681	164.7 ± 7.4
57621.20640006	167.2 ± 2.5
57621.24834448	163.4 ± 3.5
57622.14718256	157.2 ± 2.8

Figure 57: SSN 245 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

Result for SSN 245 presented in Fig. 57. The median RVs and associated errors are listed in Table 34. No HST observations for SSN 245 are available to measure the luminosity from Rickard et al. (2022).

Table 34: Radial velocities sampler results found for NGC 346 SSN 245.

MUSE Observation	Median Radial Velocity km s^{-1}
57611.32930492	167.7 ± 3.3
57613.24629853	159.3 ± 5.5
57613.28828952	188.5 ± 6.1
57617.23462962	169.4 ± 2.6
57620.19041780	166.8 ± 3.2
57620.23261681	188.1 ± 5.5
57621.20640006	169.7 ± 4.2
57621.24834448	190.9 ± 4.5
57622.14718256	178.3 ± 5.4

3 SSN 13 & SSN 15

SSN 13

Figure 58: Figure description as per Fig. 1.

SSN 13 is a hot object, previously given the spectral type of O4V((f)) (Massey et al. 1989), Result presented in Fig. 58. Dufton et al. (2019) categorise this an SB1 candidate based on their multiple epoch FLAMES observations. This object is an SB2 candidate based the analysis in this work due to the difference in the RV shift between the He I and He II lines.

Figure 59: SSN 15 Bayesian fit results. Figure description as per Fig. 1.

SSN 15 is a very hot object with a spectral type of O5.5V((f+)) (Massey et al. 1989). Result presented in Fig. 59. This target would meet the criteria set out to be considered an SB1 candidate and is classified as an SB1 candidate by Dufton et al. (2019) but instead this object is an SB2 candidate based the analysis in this work due to the difference in the RV shift between the He I and He II lines.

4 Miscellaneous target observations

This appendix shows the line segments of MUSE spectra observations of SB2 and SB3 candidate targets (Fig. 60) and Be candidate targets (Fig. 62).

Figure 60: Line segments of MUSE observations of SB2 and SB3 candidates.

Figure 61: continued.

Figure 62: Hydrogen emission features within MUSE observations of Be candidate targets.

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